

Best practices and tips for data sharing

This document outlines some best practices for data sharing in order to offer authors some guidance in line with current open research standards. It is specifically geared towards authors who are inexperienced with data sharing. Instead of delving into conceptual matters, it aims at being as specific as possible in showcasing three different possibilities of sharing your data in repositories that are widely-used in linguistics: 1) the Open Science Framework (OSF), 2) GitHub + Zenodo, and 3) the Tromsø Repository of Language and Linguistics (TroLLing).

Before turning to the individual repositories, let us briefly outline the most important best practices for data sharing that apply across platforms:

- The shared dataset(s) should be as **exhaustive** as possible, i.e. everything that a fellow researcher will need to reproduce your study should be included. Apart from raw data, this includes the analysis scripts (if applicable), which should ideally be extensively commented.
- At the same time, there will always be cases where you cannot share data for **legal and/or ethical reasons**. For example, if you have used data mining to obtain your data, you are usually not allowed to freely share it if it contains copyrighted material. Also, research data can sometimes contain sensitive information, e.g. in the case of child language corpora. In such cases, please make sure that sensitive information is removed before publication. Some repositories (e.g., Zenodo) also offer the possibility of sharing data with restricted access. If there are data that you cannot share, this is not a problem, but you should make this transparent and briefly explain why the data cannot be shared.
- Shared research data should be **FAIR, i.e. Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Retrievable**. Among other things, this means that
 - you should use **open and interoperable formats** wherever possible, e.g. CSV sheets, R or Python scripts, and avoid proprietary formats tied to specific software, e.g. .numbers or SPSS files. (Excel's .xlsx format is also an open and interoperable format, while its old .xls format, which is sometimes still used, is not.)
 - you should assign a **persistent identifier** to the dataset(s). All repositories mentioned below, as well as others, offer the possibility to assign a DOI to them.
 - your dataset should contain a **license file** that clearly states under which conditions the data can be re-used. Typically, one of the Creative Commons licenses is the ideal choice. When reusing data, e.g. from corpora, make sure to use a compatible license. For instance, when you use a dataset that is licensed CC-BY-NC-SA, this means that it can be shared for non-commercial purposes under the same or compatible conditions, i.e.

you are not allowed to release it under a CC-BY license, which allows for the data to be re-used even for commercial purposes. Please also make sure to give proper attribution to any material that you re-use.

1. OSF

The Open Science Framework is part of the infrastructure of the Center for Open Science (COS), which, among other things, also offers tools for pre-registration and for self-archiving preprints (PsyArXiv). Here we focus on its research data repository, but it might be useful to know that you can also use OSF to link preregistrations, preprints, and data repositories in one shared infrastructure.

The process of uploading research data in OSF is pretty much self-explanatory. One thing that you should know in advance is that you cannot upload entire folders (unless you zip them and upload them as a compressed file). If you have many data files that are organized hierarchically in many folders and subfolders, you may want to explore the possibility of uploading data via OSF's API, e.g. using the [osfr](#) package for R. However, in most cases, research data repositories will have a relatively simple data structure, which can also be a big advantage for future users.

For uploading data to OSF, you need a free account (no account is necessary for accessing uploaded data if they are public). After logging in, you can create a new repository, which consists of several parts:

- a **Wiki**: This is where you describe your data. We strongly recommend to add a brief explanation for every file and/or folder in your Files tab.
- **Files**: This is where you can upload your files. You can organize them in folders; as mentioned above, folders have to be created manually, unfortunately you can't just upload entire folders from your hard drive, at least not at the moment.
- **Components**: Sometimes it makes sense to organize a project into several components, especially if the size of your files exceeds the fairly generous file size limit of OSF.

Extensive guidance for using OSF can be found on their help pages. Here are a few general tips and tricks:

- OSF offers the possibility to generate **view-only links for anonymous peer review**. This feature can be found in the "Contributors" tab.
- OSF also offers the possibility of creating **DOIs** once the repository has been made public. This is highly recommended once the paper has been accepted. After acceptance, the view-only link should be replaced by the DOI link in the data availability statement. You can also consider to add the citation of your data in your list of references and to cite it in the data availability statement and wherever else in the paper it seems appropriate.

2. GitHub + Zenodo

GitHub is probably the most widely-used code sharing platform. It is not necessarily well-suited for sharing data according to the FAIR standards; for example, it doesn't offer a possibility to create persistent identifiers. However, GitHub repositories can be pushed to Zenodo, a research repository hosted by CERN.

- GitHub does not offer the possibility of creating **view-online links for peer review** natively. However, there is <https://anonymous.4open.science/>, which allows for anonymizing existing GitHub repositories. It is just a passion project by a private user, i.e. there's no guarantee that it will continue to exist for a long time, so don't forget to replace any anonymized links that you may have inserted in one of your papers for peer review by a permanent link to the non-anonymized repository, ideally the DOI.
- See <https://docs.github.com/en/repositories/archiving-a-github-repository/referencing-and-citing-content> on how to push your GitHub repository to Zenodo, which not only ensures long-term archiving of the repository but also comes with a DOI that you can cite.

3. Tromsø Repository of Language and Linguistics (TroLLing)

The unique feature of the TroLLing repository is that it was developed **specifically for linguistics**. Hosted by the University of Tromsø, it is a CLARIN Centre, i.e. part of the "Common Language Resources and Technology Infrastructure" initiative. Another crucial difference is that the TroLLing data are **curated**, i.e. your repository will be reviewed before publication. On OSF and GitHub/Zenodo, you could, in principle, publish your vacation photos instead of research data, and in the unlikely event that you have very sloppy reviewers and editors, there's a chance you might get through with it. In the case of TroLLing, your entries will be double-checked before publication. This has the additional advantage that you will almost certainly stick to the best practices of data sharing, and that you can get feedback by colleagues who are experts both in our field and in the area of open science.

Other repositories

Apart from those repositories, there are of course many more, some of which are more specialized. For example, the CHILDES repository is the de-facto standard for child language data – but typically for entire corpora, not for derived datasets such as annotated concordances. Also, CLARIN has a number of further repositories, some of which also allow for safely sharing sensitive data with restricted access, which is not possible in the case of the repositories described above (with the exception of Zenodo).